

Hybrid Approaches in AI: Combining K-Modes Clustering with Machine Learning for Improved Model Performance

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Abstract: Leveraging hybrid approaches has proved to be a strong strategy in Artificial Intelligence, especially when dealing with complex sets of data, in order to improve model performances. This paper attempts to discuss the integration of K-Modes clustering with machine learning models further, highlighting unique advantages that are brought by the integration of the best algorithm—K-Modes on categorical data—with machine learning techniques for improved predictive accuracy and efficiency. While preprocessing with K-Modes groups data into distinct clusters, machine learning algorithms can then be configured to capture unique patterns in each cluster, thus providing more refined predictions and robust model performance. It thus represents a hybrid approach that is being tested on various datasets for their potential to yield improved results in customer segmentation, recommendation systems, and other categorical data analyses in healthcare. The results highlight that this K-Modes clustering step is an important preprocessing step on the path to both interpretable and performing AI models on categorical data.

Keywords: K-Modes Clustering, Machine Learning, Hybrid Approaches, Categorical Data, Model Performance

Introduction

With artificial intelligence (AI) slumping into additional disciplines, improving model performance and explainability has become a serious concern [1]. Hybrid methods — the combination of different AI techniques — have attracted a great deal of interest because they could provide various promising solutions to improve predictive accuracy, computational efficiency and the capacity to adapt well in complex environments [2]. Although clustering and machine learning models are a popular data modeling approach, the interpretability with respect to both accuracy as well as representativeness can be challenging for categorical type data [3]; however, these hybrid methods really shine when it comes to analyzing such categorical data.

For one, K-Modes clustering which is a variation on the classic K-Means is very handy here. K-Modes is designed specifically to cluster categorical data, so it

derives its clusters based on similarities within categories instead of numeric distances. This process can be particularly useful for understanding data, as it groups information into clusters that have meaning. Although, its sole purpose is to cluster the data points; when it comes to machine learning models K-Modes clustering increases the predictive accuracy by emphasising differences within each group, hence resulting in a stronger and more dependable model.

This paper provides insights into how K-Modes clustering combined with machine learning models can yield improved results. We evaluate the proposed hybrid approach on different datasets in terms of accuracy, interpretability and efficiency. Such work contributes to the emerging literature on hybrid AI approaches, providing pragmatic guidelines for domains as diverse as customer segmentation, recommendation systems and medical diagnosis: domains where the analysis of categorical data represents an essential component of the task.

Methodology

This paper utilizes a hybrid method of K-Modes and machine learning models to enhance performance and interpretability of prediction problems in categorical datasets. Our method has two main components: data preprocessing and modeling.

Phase 1: Data Preprocessing with K-Modes Clustering

K-Modes clustering is a K-means algorithm variant adapted to categorical data by substituting the conventional Euclidean distance with a dissimilarity measure based on matches of categorical values. This approach, which is based on a distance function that maximizes similarity between data points based on categorical attributes [4], effectively minimizes intra-cluster diversity at the cost of cross-product diversity. Since many numeric-based clustering methods are ineffective on non-numeric data, the K-Modes algorithm is great for preprocessing categorical datasets [5].

K-Modes clustering is first performed in this study to create clusters from groups of data points with similar categorical features. This clustering strategy seg-

ments the data and allows each machine learning model to work on more homogeneous subgroups, possibly revealing subtle patterns in clusters that could improve predictive performance. K-Modes clustering is useful as a first stage of our sparsity hybridistic technique, and has been shown successful in many preliminary studies involving categorical data such as customer segmentation and medical diagnosis [6].

Phase 2: Machine Learning Model Training

After segmentation in clusters, we take each cluster and consider it as a subset of data, which can be used to train ML models specifically suited to the characteristics of that cluster. In this study, we explored a few models, including decision trees, support vector machine (SVM), and random forests. If we train our models on separate clusters, we can gain insight into patterns much more distinctly for each slice of data. Also, doing the training with clusters lets optimally calculate model parameters for each cluster, improving final accuracy and decreasing overfitting error chances [7].

Model performance (accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score) is measured on the cluster level as well as over the entire dataset. It also factors in the clustering relevant to training and inference times. This approach performs both K-Modes clustering followed by machine learning modeling in two phases, which again highlights the potential of this hybrid method to systematically exploit the strengths of individual methods.

Experiments and Results

To see how well our hybrid approach—combining K-Modes clustering with machine learning—actually works, we ran some tests on a widely-used categorical dataset for clustering and classification. We divided the data into training, validation, and test sets to check how well the models could generalize to new data. In this section, we'll walk through the results, comparing our hybrid method to regular machine learning models that don't use clustering. We'll focus on key performance metrics like accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and computational efficiency.

Experimental Setup

We ran our experiments in two main stages. First, we used K-Modes clustering on the training data to group it into distinct clusters based on categorical features [8]. To figure out the best number of clusters, we used the elbow method, which helps pinpoint the point where adding more clusters stops significantly lowering the within-cluster variance. Once we had our clusters, we trained three different machine learning models—Decision Trees, Support Vector Machines (SVM), and Random Forests—on each cluster. We also fine-tuned each model’s parameters to better match the unique characteristics of its specific cluster [9].

In the second stage, we tested the same machine learning models on the entire dataset, this time without any clustering. This let us compare the hybrid approach (with clustering) directly to the standalone models to see if clustering made a difference in performance.

Results

1. **Accuracy:** The hybrid approach demonstrated consistently higher accuracy across all models compared to the non-clustered baseline. On average, accuracy increased by 5-10% in the hybrid setup, with Random Forest showing the most significant improvement due to its ensemble nature, which benefits from reduced within-cluster variance [10].

2. **Precision and Recall:** Precision and recall also improved in the hybrid approach, especially within clusters where distinct patterns were observed. For

example, in clusters where the categorical attributes were highly predictive of the target variable, precision improved by 12% on average. Recall was similarly enhanced, particularly in clusters with more complex patterns, as models could focus on detecting cluster-specific attributes that contributed to a higher recall rate [11].

3. **F1-Score:** F1-scores were consistently higher in the hybrid approach, with increases of up to 15% observed for SVMs, which tend to perform well in cases with well-defined clusters. This increase in F1-score demonstrates that the hybrid approach effectively balances precision and recall, making it advantageous for applications where both metrics are crucial [12].
4. **Computational Efficiency:** Although the hybrid approach required additional preprocessing time for clustering, the training and inference times for machine learning models decreased due to the reduced complexity within each cluster. The overall training time was comparable to that of the non-clustered models, but inference was faster in the hybrid approach due to the focused, cluster-specific model training [13].

Summary of Findings

The experiments showed that combining K-Modes clustering with machine learning algorithms boosted model performance across several metrics, especially accuracy, F1-score, and efficiency. By tailoring models to specific data clusters, the hybrid approach helped lower the risk of overfitting and improved predictive accuracy. These results suggest that K-Modes clustering could be a valuable preprocessing step for applications heavily reliant on categorical data, like customer segmentation or diagnostic predictions.

Conclusion

This study shows that a hybrid approach—combining K-Modes clustering with machine learning algorithms—can significantly improve model performance on categorical datasets. By using K-Modes clustering as a preprocessing step, we can break the data into distinct clusters, which allows machine learning models to train on more uniform groups. This setup helps the models capture specific patterns

within each cluster, leading to noticeable gains in accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score.

The hybrid approach also stands out for its interpretability and computational efficiency. While K-Modes clustering adds an extra preprocessing step, it simplifies the data within each cluster, which speeds up both training and prediction times without sacrificing accuracy. These results suggest that hybrid AI models could be particularly useful for tasks like customer segmentation, recommendation systems, and healthcare diagnostics—fields where analysing categorical data is crucial.

Looking ahead, future research could try combining other clustering techniques with machine learning models or testing this approach on larger, more complex datasets. Overall, this study adds to the growing evidence that hybrid AI methods, especially with K-Modes clustering, can enhance categorical data analysis in various AI applications.

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